

Destructive Effects of Endotoxins on Inflammatory and Hepato-renal Function Indices, and Protective Role of 17 β -estradiol therapy

Saif Mohammed Hamzah¹, Goljameen Midhat Abdulla², Ozdan Akram Ghareeb^{3*}

¹Basic Sciences Department, Dentistry College, Wasit University, Iraq .

^{2,3}Pharmacy Department, Medical Technical Institute / Kirkuk, Northern Technical University, Iraq

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19508908>

Article Received 15-02-2026 / Article Accepted 08-04-2026 / Article Published 11-04-2026

ABSTRACT:

Background: Endotoxin, also known as lipopolysaccharide (LPS), is a potent activator of the innate immune system, which induces a systemic inflammatory response syndrome which may progress to septic shock.

Objective: To investigate potential protective role of 17 β -Estradiol therapy against endotoxin (LPS)-induced inflammation and organ dysfunction in ovariectomized laboratory female rats.

Methods: In this experiment, fifty adult female rats were employed to compare the effects of endotoxin (LPS), estrogen (E2), and their combination. They are set randomly into five groups (ten in each group) as follows: CON, LPS, E2+LPS, LPS+E2, and E2. Laboratory tests were conducted to assess hepato-renal function, and inflammatory serum biomarkers in all experimental groups.

Results: The results showed a significant difference in the serum levels of inflammatory, renal, and hepatic parameters in LPS rats when compared to control rats. Both pre-treatment and co-treatment with estrogen markedly reduced serum levels of these analyzed indices compared with the LPS group.

Conclusions: Estrogen has significant anti-inflammatory and hepato-renal protective effects against LPS-induced damage in rats.

Keywords: Endotoxin, Inflammatory cytokines, hepato-renal dysfunction.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Copyright (c) 2026 **Ozdan Akram Ghareeb**

How to Cite

Saif Mohammed Hamzah, Goljameen Midhat Abdulla, Ozdan Akram Ghareeb. (2026). Destructive Effects of Endotoxins on Inflammatory and Hepato-renal Function Indices, and Protective Role of 17 β -estradiol therapy. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Academic Research*, 7(02), 16-23. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19508908>

INTRODUCTION:

Lipopolysaccharide (LPS), which is a central component of the outer membrane in Gram-negative bacteria, is known to be an effective systemic inflammation inducer [1]. Following intraperitoneal injection, LPS activates innate immune cells, including macrophages and monocytes, leading to an uncontrolled secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) [2]. These cytokines mediate a strong inflammatory response and lead to immune cell recruitment, oxidative stress, and cellular damage [3,4]. In general, persistent or excessive cytokine production can lead to systemic inflammatory responses, multi-organ dysfunction, and, in severe cases, septic shock [5,6].

17 β -estradiol the most potent estrogen, is chiefly responsible for the classical regulation of female reproductive physiology. However, growing evidence has revealed that estrogen also has systemic effects, including anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidative, and immune modulatory effects [7,8]. It supports organ preservation by down-regulating pro-inflammatory cytokine expression, dampening immune activation, and reducing oxidative stress [9].

It is noteworthy that low levels of estrogen (potentially starting at the time of ovariectomy or after menopause) promote an inflammatory and oxidant state and increase the risk of organ injury, highlighting the importance of estrogen in the immune system and in maintenance of tissue homeostasis [10,11]. Experimental studies including animal models have confirmed that therapy with 17 β -estradiol reduces LPS-induced inflammatory responses by inhibiting TNF- α and IL-6 expression, thus preventing cell injury and improving organ function [12]. However, the exact mechanisms of estrogen protection against endotoxin-induced organ injury are still unclear [13]. Due to the prominent role of the liver and kidneys in detoxification, metabolism and excretion of harmful substances, these organs are

especially susceptible to damage caused by LPS [14,15]. Hepatic injury commonly presents with hepatocellular necrosis and increased liver enzymes, and renal injury can lead to decreased filtration and high creatinine and urea; both of these pathways underline the vital importance of treatments that would alter inflammatory pathways to protect organ function [16,17]. Adult rats, being both reliable and controlled, serve as a good model for these effects, with cytokine modulation, immune response, and organ protection explored in detail [18,19]. The present study aimed to investigate the protective effects of 17 β -estradiol therapy against endotoxin-induced inflammation and organ dysfunction in ovariectomized rats.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Experimental Design

This experiment was designed using fifty adult female Wistar rats aged between (3-4) weeks and weighing between (210-270g), obtained from animal house of Veterinary Medicine College, University of Kirkuk, Iraq. They acclimated under ideal laboratory environment (12-hour light/dark cycle, controlled temperature, and 50–60% humidity) with free access to food and water for seven days before starting experiment.

They were set into five primary groups (ten in each group): Group 1 (CON): Rats without any treatment only for control; Group 2 (LPS): Sham (placebo)-operated rats received a single intraperitoneal (ip) injection of lipopolysaccharide (LPS, 10 mg/kg). Group 3 (E2 + LPS): Ovariectomized (OVX) rats were pre-treated with estrogen (17 β -estradiol, 1 mg/kg/day, subcutaneously) in sesame oil for 7 days prior to LPS administration. Group 4 (LPS + E2): OVX rats were co-treated with LPS and estrogen with same doses. Group 4 (E2): Ovariectomized rats were subjected to estrogen replacement therapy alone without any LPS exposure. After the experiment was completed, the samples were collected accurately and biochemical laboratory

analyses were conducted using special commercial kits and according to the companies' instructions for liver and kidney parameters. Levels of inflammatory cytokines were measured using commercial ELISA kits. All of the ELISA assays and statistical analyses were performed using coded labels to eliminate any potential bias in the analysis of the data. All experimental procedures adhered to the ethical guidelines for animal research, as outlined in the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals.

Statistical Analysis:

Table 1: Toxic effects of LPS on some serum biochemical parameters in experiment rats.

Parameters	G1-CON	G2-LPS
TNF- α (pg/mL)	224.7 \pm 45.02	713.1 \pm 117.8*
IL-6 (pg/mL)	611.7 \pm 175.6	1868 \pm 393.2*
MCP-1 (pg/mL)	294.1 \pm 30.23	881.4 \pm 184.0*
ALT (U/L)	98.13 \pm 14.52	197.2 \pm 22.10*
AST (U/L)	192.4 \pm 24.15	406.2 \pm 50.09*
Creatinine (mg/dL)	1.03 \pm 0.12	2.009 \pm 0.292*
Urea (mg/dL)	33.13 \pm 4.11	67.65 \pm 8.037*

As shown in tables (2 and 3), pre-treatment with estrogen before treated with LPS (G3- E2+LPS group) as well as in (G4-LPS+E2) ovariectomized

rats, results demonstrated clear lowering levels (p-value < 0.05) in these serum indicators when compared with LPS rats

Table 2: Compared between pre-treatment E2+LPS with LPS rats.

Parameters	G2-LPS	G3- E2+LPS
TNF- α (pg/mL)	713.1 \pm 117.8	405.8 \pm 56.74*
IL-6 (pg/mL)	1868 \pm 393.2	862.3 \pm 177.1*
MCP-1 (pg/mL)	881.4 \pm 184.0	458.7 \pm 79.24*
ALT (U/L)	197.2 \pm 22.10	107.8 \pm 10.73*
AST (U/L)	406.2 \pm 50.09	205.7 \pm 26.89*
Creatinine (mg/dL)	2.009 \pm 0.2922	1.217 \pm 0.093*
Urea (mg/dL)	67.65 \pm 8.037	44.39 \pm 4.639*

Table 3: Compared between co-treatment LPS+E2 with LPS rats.

Parameters	G2-LPS	G4-LPS+E2
TNF- α (pg/mL)	713.1 \pm 117.8	267.9 \pm 53.04*
IL-6 (pg/mL)	1868 \pm 393.2	671.3 \pm 145.9*
MCP-1 (pg/mL)	881.4 \pm 184.0	302.0 \pm 60.79*
ALT (U/L)	197.2 \pm 22.10	107.3 \pm 16.52*
AST (U/L)	406.2 \pm 50.09	201.7 \pm 32.36*
Creatinine (mg/dL)	2.009 \pm 0.292	1.070 \pm 0.163*
Urea (mg/dL)	67.65 \pm 8.037	35.43 \pm 6.236*

Similarly, G5-E2 was compared with a group of rats receiving combined treatment, receiving a dose of 10 mg/kg LPS and simultaneously receiving a 1 mg/kg/day dose of 17 β -estradiol treatment (E2+LPS) and (LPS+E2) groups, as shown in Tables (4,5).

Table 4: Compared between only estrogen E2 with E2+LPS in studied rats.

Parameters	G5-E2	G3- E2+LPS
TNF- α (pg/mL)	10.70 \pm 2.914	405.8 \pm 56.74*
IL-6 (pg/mL)	18.48 \pm 4.209	862.3 \pm 177.1*
MCP-1 (pg/mL)	45.39 \pm 10.20	458.7 \pm 79.24*
ALT (U/L)	37.43 \pm 3.396	107.8 \pm 10.73*
AST (U/L)	71.43 \pm 5.735	205.7 \pm 26.89*
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.640 \pm 0.062	1.217 \pm 0.093*
Urea (mg/dL)	32.70 \pm 3.483	44.39 \pm 4.639*

Table 5: Compared between only estrogen E2 with LPS+E2 in studied rats.

Parameters	G5-E2	G4-LPS+E2
TNF- α (pg/mL)	10.70 \pm 2.914	267.9 \pm 53.04*
IL-6 (pg/mL)	18.48 \pm 4.209	671.3 \pm 145.9*
MCP-1 (pg/mL)	45.39 \pm 10.20	302.0 \pm 60.79*
ALT (U/L)	37.43 \pm 3.396	107.3 \pm 16.52*
AST (U/L)	71.43 \pm 5.735	201.7 \pm 32.36*
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.640 \pm 0.062	1.070 \pm 0.163*
Urea (mg/dL)	32.70 \pm 3.483	35.43 \pm 6.236

DISCUSSION:

The results demonstrated that administration of estrogen (E2) significantly attenuated the LPS-induced elevations in some immunological, hepatic, and renal markers. For this performance, serum levels of immunological parameters were elevated significantly in the LPS-treated group, which was proof of a prominent systemic inflammatory response after endotoxin exposure. Concomitant treatment with estrogen (LPS + E2 group) dramatically lowered these cytokines ($p < 0.05$), indicating a marked anti-inflammatory potency of estrogen.

The decrease in TNF- α and IL-6 implies an inhibited NF- κ B signaling pathway and decreased transcription of pro-inflammatory genes, and the decrease in MCP-1 indicates decreased monocyte recruitment and chemotactic activity within hepatic and renal tissues [20]. In addition, compared with the LPS group, serum ALT and AST activities were markedly lower in the LPS + E2 group, indicating restoration of hepatocellular membranes from endotoxin-induced injury [21]. The preservation of hepatic integrity is likely attributed to the antioxidant capacity of estrogen, stabilization of mitochondrial function, or suppression of reactive oxygen species formation [22].

The significant decrease in serum creatinine and urea levels by estrogen in rats is also a marker of renal function, as well as a reduction in glomerular injury. The renal protective effect can be mediated through interference either estrogen induced up-regulation of endothelial nitric oxide synthase or enhance renal blood flow and inhibition of inflammatory cytokine infiltration within renal tissues [23]. During endotoxin exposure, estrogen has dual anti-inflammatory and organ-protective effects by regulating cytokines, oxidative stress, and endothelial function. These biochemical findings highlight the potential therapeutic relevance of estrogen or estrogenic compounds to reduce LPS-induced hepatic and renal dysfunction [24].

In E2 + LPS group there was a significant reduction of serum immunological parameters concentrations compared with LPS group, which was indicative of a robust attenuation of the inflammatory cascade. This indicates estrogen was capable of effectively down regulating the NF- κ B-dependent transcription of pro-inflammatory genes, thereby limiting the release of cytokines from activated macrophages and Kupffer cells [25].

Apart from its potent anti-inflammatory activity, estrogen also provides strong hepato-protective and reno-protective properties, as reflected by the decreases in serum ALT and AST levels, as well as creatinine and urea concentrations [26]. The protective effects of estrogen in preserving hepatic and renal function are likely due to its anti-oxidative properties, its membrane-stabilizing effects, and its ability to enhance nitric oxide-mediated vasodilation, which would maintain tissue perfusion and decrease ischemic damage during endotoxemia [27].

The estrogen-pretreatment exerts a protective effect against LPS-induced inflammatory and organ dysfunction, mainly via the inhibition of overproduction of pro-inflammatory cytokines and the preservation of oxidative anti-oxidant balance. This provides further evidence that the timing of estrogen administration affects the response of the host to endotoxin exposure [28].

According to contents of hepatic (ALT and AST) and renal (creatinine and urea) functions disturbances were significantly higher in LPS + E2, but not in estrogen alone group indicating persistent hepatic stress and renal dysfunction due to LPS. Thus, these data indicate that, while the anti-inflammatory and tissue protective effects of estrogen are lessened by concurrent administration, the protective efficacy of estrogen when inflammation has already developed is only partially inhibited. In summary, these results suggest that under resting, non-inflammatory conditions, estrogen maintains low baseline levels

of cytokines and protective against hepatic and renal tissue [29].

Under septic stress, these protective effects break down but remain evident with moderate elevations in all biochemistry parameters compared to the LPS-only group. Such a result may back up the hypothesis of the protective potential of estrogen being more protective as a pre-treatment compared to the concurrent therapy against endotoxin-induced damage [30]. The estrogen group (alone) had low total baseline cytokine levels (TNF- α , IL-6, and MCP-1), consistent with the role of estrogen in immune homeostasis by functionally suppressing pro-inflammatory gene expression and up-regulating anti-inflammatory mediators [31].

This effect is probably facilitated via stimulation of estrogen receptors (ER- α and ER- β), resulting in suppression of the NF- κ B pathway, abolition of oxidative stress, and preservation of endothelial nitric oxide synthase activity with the ultimate maintenance of cell integrity and organ perfusion in the presence of systemic inflammation [32]. Finally, these results confirm that estrogen pre-treatment attenuates but does not completely prevent the harmful effects of endotoxin, indicating that the protection by the hormone may be most effective if started before inflammatory insult [33].

CONCLUSION:

Estrogen has prominent anti-inflammatory, hepato-protective, and reno-protective effects against LPS-induced damage in rats, and attenuates endotoxin-induced systemic inflammatory and organ dysfunction, possibly by modulating cytokine production and improving endothelial function. These effects increased when given prior exposure to endotoxin.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

There is no conflict of interest in this paper

REFERENCES:

- 1- Thiyagarajan S, Bhaskar E, Gayathri V, Mohanalakshmi P, Silambanan S. Lipopolysaccharide as a biomarker of gut dysbiosis in diabetic Wistar rats—A pre-clinical experimental study. *Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*. 2025 Oct:1-6.
- 2- Benmhammed H, Lamtai M, Mesfioui A, Nassiri A, Mouden S, Bikri S, Hessni AE. Effects of lipopolysaccharide administration at different postnatal periods on behavioral and biochemical assessments in Wistar rats. *Neuroscience and Behavioral Physiology*. 2024 Mar;54(3):357-73.
- 3- Al-hashemi, Hadeel. "Effects of two types of statins in lipid profile of ovariectomized female rats." *NTU Journal of Pure Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 2, 2023.
- 4- Ghareeb OA, Abdulla GM, Sheikhzadeh S. Evaluation of proinflammatory cytokines in arsenic induced hepatotoxicity in vivo. *Journal of Animal Health and Production*. 2024;12(s1):196-201.
- 5- Monti G, Carta S, Kotani Y, Bruni A, Konkayeva M, Guarracino F, Yakovlev A, Cucciolini G, Shemetova M, Scapol S, Momesso E. A Multinational Randomized Trial of Mega-Dose Esomeprazole as Anti-Inflammatory Agent in Sepsis. *Critical care medicine*. 2025 Jun 25;53(8):e1554-66.
- 6- Ghareeb OA, Roy D, Nazeer N, Abbas M, Ruzieva M, Avazmetova I, Abilkasimov A, Dadabaeva R, Rao DP. Complementary effects of polyphenolic nutraceuticals in enhancing antioxidant defense and immunity of *Labeo rohita*. *Aquaculture International*. 2026 Feb 17;34(3):75.
- 7- Lemini C, García-Albor E, Cruz-López B, Matamoros-Trejo G, Márquez-Baltazar S, Herrera-Pérez JJ, Martínez-Mota L. Prolame produces anxiolytic-and antidepressant-like effects in middle-aged female rats with less uterotrophic effects than 17 β -estradiol.

- European Journal of Pharmacology. 2024 Apr 15;969:176454.
- 8- Leonel EC, Campos SG, Guerra LH, Bedolo CM, Vilamaior PS, Calmon MF, Rahal P, Amorim CA, Taboga SR. Impact of perinatal bisphenol A and 17 β estradiol exposure: Comparing hormone receptor response. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*. 2020 Jan 30;188:109918.
- 9- Scheld M, Heymann F, Zhao W, Tohidnezhad M, Clarner T, Beyer C, Zendedel A. Modulatory effect of 17 β -estradiol on myeloid cell infiltration into the male rat brain after ischemic stroke. *The Journal of Steroid Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*. 2020 Sep 1;202:105667.
- 10- Ghareeb OA. Deleterious effects of inflammatory cytokines induced by endotoxin on hepato-renal functions and attenuating role of estrogen in vivo. *Agricultural Biotechnology Journal*. 2026 Mar 21;18(1):259-80.
- 11- Pearce P, LaFrancois JJ, Skucas V, Friedman D, Fenton AA, Dvorak D, MacLusky NJ, Scharfman HE. Testosterone and 17 β -estradiol regulate hippocampal area CA3 sharp waves in male and female rats. *Cell reports*. 2025 Jul 22;44(7).
- 12- Conrad CD, Peay DN, Sladkova S, Kim JL, Donnay ME, Acuña AM, Whittaker KE. Chronic 17 β -estradiol treatment improves negative valence, anhedonic profile, and social interactions in ovariectomized, middle-aged female rats. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*. 2025 Jul 2;19:1553501.
- 13- El-Khatib YA, Sayed RH, Sallam NA, Zaki HF, Khattab MM. 17 β -Estradiol augments the neuroprotective effect of agomelatine in depressive-and anxiety-like behaviors in ovariectomized rats. *Psychopharmacology*. 2020 Sep;237(9):2873-86.
- 14- Ghareeb OA, Ali QA. Hepatotoxicity induced by some metal nanoparticles in vivo. *J. Clin. Med. Rev*. Vol. 2024;3(1):017.
- 15- Yousif, S.W., Taqa , G.A., Ameer M. Taha,A.,M. "Anti-inflammatory and Protective Effects of Melatonin on Rats Exposed to Anticancer Drugs" . *NTU Journal of Pure Sciences*. vol.2, no.2,pp.6-14, 2023.
- 16- Ahmed FF, Ghareeb OA, Al-Bayti AA. Nephro defensive efficiency of cichorium intybus against toxicity caused by copper oxide nanoparticles. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2022;16(03):542-52.
- 17- Tahoun E, Elgedawy G, El-Bahrawy A. Cytoprotective effect of ginger extract on cisplatin-induced hepatorenal toxicity in rats via modulation of oxidative stress, inflammation and apoptosis: histopathological, biochemical and immunohistochemical study. *Comparative Clinical Pathology*. 2021 Aug;30(4):647-63.
- 18- Ghareeb OA, Sheikhzadeh S. Single Dose of Chloroform Induces Hepatic Dysfunction with Pro-Inflammatory Cytokines Response in Vivo. *South Eastern European Journal of Public Health*. 2024:747-53.
- 19- Bekheit RA, Aboulthana WM, Serag WM. Assessment of the biological efficacy of gold Nannochloropsis oculata nano-extract against lithium-induced toxicity in rats. *Scientific Reports*. 2026 Jan 26;16(1):3269.
- 20- Reema P, Grock S, Wolfe HL, Jackson N, Neugarten J, Hashemi L. Kidney Health and Gender-Affirming Hormone Therapy for Transgender and Gender Diverse Individuals. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*. 2025 Mar 1:10-2215.
- 21- Turan B, Asci H, Imeci O, Tepebasi M, Ulusoy A, Acar S, Karaca I, Akpınar O, Ozmen O. Synergistic mitigation of endotoxin-induced liver injury by low-frequency PMF and 27.12 MHz RF-EMF: a multi-biomarker experimental study. *European Journal of Trauma and Emergency Surgery*. 2026 Feb 23;52(1):56.
- 22- Vojtechova I, Maleninska K, Kutna V, Klovrcza O, Tuckova K, Petrsek T, Stuchlik

- A. Behavioral alterations and decreased number of parvalbumin-positive interneurons in Wistar rats after maternal immune activation by lipopolysaccharide: sex matters. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2021 Mar 23;22(6):3274.
- 23- Marbouti L, Zahmatkesh M, Riahi E, Sadr SS. Inhibition of brain 17 β -estradiol synthesis by letrozole induces cognitive decline in male and female rats. *Neurobiology of learning and memory*. 2020 Nov 1;175:107300.
- 24- Liu M, Guo P, Zeng M, Zhang Y, Jia J, Liu Y, Chen X, Kuang H, Feng W, Zheng X. Effects and mechanisms of frefmaglutin D and rehmaionoside C improve LPS-induced acute kidney injury through the estrogen receptor-mediated TLR4 pathway in vivo and in vitro. *Phytomedicine*. 2024 Jan 1;123:155218.
- 25- Dorrigiv M, Zareiyan A, Hosseinzadeh H. Garlic (*Allium sativum*) as an antidote or a protective agent against natural or chemical toxicities: A comprehensive update review. *Phytotherapy Research*. 2020 Aug;34(8):1770-97.
- 26- Osen FA, Yakubu MT, Balogun EA, Salau A. Biochemical and histoarchitectural changes in the liver, kidney and heart after oral administration of *Viscum album* leaf extract in oestradiol valerate-treated female rats. *Algerian journal of Biosciences*. 2024 Jun 30;5(01):001-12.
- 27- Magata F, Toda L, Sato M, Sakono T, Chambers JK, Uchida K, Tsukamura H, Matsuda F. Intrauterine LPS inhibited arcuate Kiss1 expression, LH pulses, and ovarian function in rats. *Reproduction*. 2022 Nov 1;164(5):207-19.
- 28- Harding AT, Heaton NS. The impact of estrogens and their receptors on immunity and inflammation during infection. *Cancers*. 2022 Feb 12;14(4):909.
- 29- Tajanko FN, Muller CR, Munoz C, Cabrales P. Modulatory Effects of Exogenous Estradiol during Endotoxemia. *The International Journal of Biochemistry & Cell Biology*. 2026 Feb 20:106919.
- 30- Alewel DI, Rentschler KM, Schladweiler MC, Miller CN, Gavett SH, Evansky PA, Grindstaff R, Williams WC, Kodavanti UP. Estrogen and glucocorticoid receptors co-regulate acrolein-induced respiratory and systemic homeostatic stress responses. *Toxicological Sciences*. 2025 Sep;207(1):109-25.
- 31- Morsi AA, Mersal EA, Abdelmoneim AM, Hussein G, Sofii MM, Ibrahim KE, Salim MS. Interrogating the estrogen-mediated regulation of adrenocortical klotho expression using ovariectomized albino rat model exposed to repeated restraint stress. *Human Cell*. 2024 Jul;37(4):1008-23.
- 32- Kosyрева AM, Dzhililova DS, Makarova OV, Tsvetkov IS, Zolotova NA, Diatroptova MA, Ponomarenko EA, Mkhitarov VA, Khochanskiy DN, Mikhailova LP. Sex differences of inflammatory and immune response in pups of Wistar rats with SIRS. *Scientific reports*. 2020 Sep 28;10(1):15884.
- 33- Mostagir A, Halawa A, Elmetwally M, Lashen S, Rezk S, Abdallah A, Saed H, Shalaby N, Hammad A, Bazeed S. Lipopolysaccharide affects the oxidative stress markers and angiogenic and IGF1 mRNA expression in the uterus and ovaries of Wistar albino rats. *Acta Veterinaria Eurasia*. 2024 Jan 19;50(1):47-57.